

THE DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL TOURISM: EXAMINING BENEFITS, CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR GROWTH

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of rural tourism by examining its benefits, such as the noticeable economic impact that improves the local citizens' living standards in rural places. Meanwhile, it analyses the contemporary state of this sphere, the key problems and challenges, including a lack of infrastructure, a shortage of professionals in this sphere, and environmental problems, the article gives some strategies and solutions for the development of rural tourism in Uzbekistan, namely infrastructure enhancement, training and professionalizing, investing and funding that can help to minimize the mentioned challenges.*

Keywords: *rural tourism, Uzbekistan, social and environmental sustainability, cultural and natural heritage, tourism industry, living standards*

Literature Review. The article written by Qarajanova Gulnoza is the number one reliable source for my essay because of mentioning “*the Benefits of Rural Tourism Development*”, “*Problems and Challenges of the Rural Tourism Sector*”, etc., as some of the body paragraphs of my essay need information from this resource. Cornelia Petroman, Sandal Palade...’s article is another source for my essay which assists me in another body, due to suggesting some major strategies. Another article called “*Analysis of the Current Situation of Rural Tourism in Uzbekistan*” is helpful to me because one of the body paragraphs of my essay is about the influences of COVID-19 on Rural Tourism Development. The situation after the pandemic, which caused the creation of some extra and some new jobs, is contained in this article. Therefore, in this part of my essay, I will use this article. Written by Yung-Lun Liu, Lui-Te Chiang & Pen-Fa Ko, the article contains reliable information in the body paragraph first and mentions the number of benefits of another type of Rural tourism (community development). In the article “*Strategies and Directions for the Development of Rural Tourism*”, I can find some strategies and directions to develop Rural Tourism. One of the body paragraphs of my essay is about the strategies. This article gives me very demanding strategies with the definition and how it works while using, thus I need this article.

Introduction. Rural tourism is an exclusive opportunity for sustainability and improving rural economic development, particularly for countries like Uzbekistan, because the place is rich in cultural and natural heritage. “This type of tourism allows the local population to use their natural, historical, and cultural resources to attract tourists, which, in turn, contributes to increasing incomes and improving the quality of life. Uzbekistan, a country with a rich historical past and unique natural landscapes, is an important destination for rural tourism development. With more than 74,000 cultural heritage locations, including ancient cities [like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva,] and mausoleums, the country has considerable prospects to attract travellers from different places of the world” (Qarajanova, 2023). “**Rural Tourism** is a type of tourism activity in which the visitor’s experience is related to a wide range of products generally linked to nature-based activities, agriculture, rural lifestyle/culture, angling, and sightseeing” (UNWTO, n.d.). While rural tourism development in Uzbekistan increases the income of the local population and preserves cultural and natural heritage, at the same time it contributes to the

diversification of the economy, and enhancing infrastructure. Although rural tourism has several benefits mentioned before, it faces several challenges, such as a lack of infrastructure, a shortage of skilled workers, and environmental concerns. To fully realize its potential, it is vital to mitigate the mentioned problems through several clear and strong strategies and directions named as enhancing infrastructure, local training programs, investment, and financing. This article aims to understand the role of rural tourism in Uzbekistan by analyzing the current situation of rural tourism and discussing possible directions and strategies for developing this sector, which could be beneficial to residents and the country as a whole.

Figure 1

The preference of participants whether they go to the countryside often or not

3. Do you often go rural areas?

19 ответов

Note: People who participated in the questionnaire, more than half (63,2%), prefer going to rural areas to relax or enjoy the natural habitat.

Benefits of Rural Tourism

Developing rural tourism in Uzbekistan is not just about boosting the economy; it's also a chance to promote social and environmental sustainability. This initiative intertwines culture, history, nature, and the economy, creating lasting value that goes far beyond the direct profits from tourism.

From one perspective, rural tourism has a perceptible economic impact because it enhances the local citizens' living standards. Tourism in rural areas boosts the need for regional goods and services, generates employment, and fosters entrepreneurship, particularly in the sectors of agriculture, handicrafts, and services, thus supporting and diversifying the local economy (Qarajanova, 2023). Based on the points made by Qarajanova, the economic significance of rural tourism seems short-term profits. Because of the increasing desire for local services and goods, it will help to grow small businesses, making the economy more diversified and self-sufficient to one industry, like farming. As a result of this action, it will be the reason to create new jobs, keeping younger citizens in rural areas, or otherwise those might move to urban places to search for a job. Therefore, rural tourism can assist bring new life to these communities, encouraging local entrepreneurship, which helps those people to pride in their businesses.

Moreover, rural tourism is also vital in safeguarding both cultural and natural heritage. By exploring rural areas, visitors gain a strong appreciation for the local traditions, customs, and lifestyles, which in turn encourages people to protect historical landmarks, traditional customs, languages, arts, and the environment (Askarova et al., 2023). This emphasizes how taking action on rural tourism as a bridge among generations, developing a sense of honor in the local population. By interacting with tourists, locals can often strengthen the importance of their cultural traditions and customs which heartens their protection of customs for the future.

Togaymurodov et al. say “At the same time, the effective development of rural tourism requires a thoughtful approach and cooperation between various actors: government, business, local communities, and tourists. Taking into account these [the need for cooperation and thoughtful approach] aspects, rural tourism can become one of the key factors of sustainable development in Uzbekistan, benefiting all participants in the process and ensuring the long-term well-being of rural areas” (2023). This statement emphasizes the significance of partnership among these stakeholders for the prosperous growth of rural tourism. Furthermore, through these collaborations, the government can create policies to ensure cultural and natural heritage protection that promotes sustainable tourism. Local communities can pride in their traditions and customs as well as allow travelers to experience regional rituals. Meanwhile, tourists can support the local economy of that place by purchasing locally-made products, such as souvenirs, and services. Thus, they might help develop small businesses in rural areas through these actions.

Figure 2

The participants’ opinion on the benefits of visiting the rural places

5. What do you think, how people can bring benefits to economy through going rural areas? Write your own answer.

19 ответов

Note: People mainly think that a benefit to rural areas through their travels is supporting local businesses as a percentage of 57,9%, while tourism development and job creation are the second benefit in terms of percentage 47,4% respectively.

Current Analyses of Uzbekistan’s Rural Tourism

After the COVID-19 pandemic, which has considerably influenced the worldwide tourism industry, including Uzbekistan, the country is dedicated to restoring and enhancing this sector. Rural tourism is very essential component of the nation’s economic recovery and growth plan.

According to Qarajanova, “Uzbekistan has developed a "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [7 main strategies have been defined], which includes plans to triple the volume of tourism services and create 3.5 million new jobs. It is estimated that the number of domestic tourists will reach more than 12 million, while the number of foreign tourists will reach 9 million” (2023). This development plan focuses on the demanding approach of Uzbekistan to the growth of the country’s tourism sphere. Uzbekistan aims to create millions of new job opportunities and enhance its economy by remarkably raising the number of domestic and

international visitors. Due to achieving these goals, the country can enhance infrastructure and promote cultural replacement as well.

Figure 3

“The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”

“During the pandemic, decisions were made to support the industry, including exempting tour operators, travel agents, and hotels from land and property taxes until December 31, 2020, and reducing social taxes. These measures have helped to reduce the financial burden on tourism-related businesses” (Askarova et al., 2023).

Creating Jobs and Improving Living Standards

Because of the creation of new job opportunities, tourism is considered the key sector that is significantly crucial for the country’s citizens who seek work abroad. The industry of tourism can present jobs in the sector of service, hotels, restaurants, and also craft workshops, and souvenir production in small businesses. “Uzbekistan is making significant strides in the development of rural tourism as an important part of its economy, aimed at improving rural life and preserving cultural heritage” (Qarajanova, 2023). Based on Qarajanova’s opinion, tourism is very crucial in creating jobs and enhancing the local people’s lifestyles, particularly for people seeking job in foreign countries. For instance, while tourism provides employment opportunities, it keeps people engaged in their local communities, and therefore reducing the need to seek work abroad. This supports economic self-reliance and sustains families locally. In my opinion, tourism can support small businesses because of strengthening tourism-related activities, such as the production of souvenirs and craft workshops which are mentioned by Qarajanova. In Uzbekistan, on an account of improving the economy and protecting cultural traditions, rural tourism plays a very vital role. To make it better, improving things like building better infrastructure, improving education, marketing, and working with other countries are needed. These steps will help tourism grow in a way that lasts and also ensure that the country’s heritage is preserved while keeping up with modern changes.

Problems of Rural Tourism Enhancement in Uzbekistan

Developing rural tourism in Uzbekistan, despite its remarkable prospects, is facing some challenges that may slow or restrain its rise and success.

According to Alieva & Yoriyeva, these challenges are mentioned:

A Lack of Infrastructure: A lack of infrastructure, such as roads, transport, communications, and tourist facilities, especially in rural areas is considered as one of the main

challenges. This makes access to their destinations difficult and lowers the quality of tourism services (2023). This makes it harder for travellers to reach their desired destinations because poor roads, as well as limited transportation, can lead to trips of tourists longer and take their time to get to that place more, additionally will cause to spend higher costs. Furthermore, weak communication networks, like poor internet, the location of unfamiliar places, and phone signals, make the travel of tourists harder to plan and feel safe during their trip. As a result, the sector of tourism in these areas struggles to grow, and limits economic opportunities for citizens preventing them to benefit from natural beauty.

A Shortage of Skilled Workers: Because of the lack of professionals in tourism management, hospitality, and marketing, it is harder to offer high-quality and professional tourism services (2023). This is another problem that rural tourism faces and a lack of well-qualified workers makes the businesses difficult in the tourism, because visitors who travel to rural places often expect high-quality services, productive and customer-focused experiences. Thus, the service quality that tourists suffer can decrease the customer satisfaction.

Environmental Concerns: The quick development of tourism without proper measures to protect and preserve nature, can damage the loss of natural resources, the reducing of biodiversity, and worsen environmental conditions (2023). Without proper preservation in tourism can cause considerable harm to the environment. It can result to a loss of natural resources, such as water, and damage to ecosystems. Because the tourists visit to the natural places, the increased demand for activities they do gives rise to worsening environmental conditions.

By 2023, it is said that: In many countries, urban areas are more developed than rural areas. Rural places are almost always considered to have many challenges, including low productivity, and low income. Other problems include population shifts from rural areas to cities, the shortage of growing the economy, dropping the opportunities of workers, the mislaying of farms, the influence on historical and cultural heritage, sharp demographic changes, and low life quality. And continuing these agricultural practices without any changes could lead to more significant social issues in rural areas (Liu et al.,)

Figure 4

The participants’ view on the main problems of rural tourism in Uzbekistan

6. For you, which one of these challenges is often faced in rural areas?

19 ответов

Note: People mainly think as a number one problem in rural areas is a lack of qualified workers (57,9%), while the rest two are considered as 52,6% and 42,1%.

Strategies and Solutions for Uzbekistan’s Rural Tourism Development

To achieve sustainable rural tourism development in Uzbekistan and maximize its long-term benefits to both local populations and the wider economy, some well-structured strategies and clear development directions should be required.

1. **Enhancing infrastructure:** Upgrading the accessibility and condition of tourism infrastructure in the countryside—such as transportation, lodging, and communication services—is the key to drawing tourists. Creating tourist routes, information centers and proper signage is also critical for a victorious tourism experience (Qarajanova, 2023). Improving transportation, lodging, and communication services ensures that tourists can easily get to that place without any troubles, and therefore enjoy their destinations. Meanwhile, creating well-designed routes, signage and information centres is also crucial that can provide pleasurable experiences during the traveller’s trip.
2. **Local Training Programs:** Providing local residents with training in tourism management, hospitality, marketing, and language will elevate the service quality and in tourism increase professionalism and attractiveness (Petromen et al., 2023). Local Training Programs are very vital to enhance the tourism service qualities. By providing some practices in rural places namely tourism management, hospitality, marketing, and languages, local people can develop the needed skills in tourism to present well-qualified services. This not only helps to cut a shortage of skilled workers and develop the number of them but also makes the places more attractive to tourists, because visitors often want to have very memorable experiences with a well-trained and educated workforce. As a result, this kind of programs can be a good example to develop the economy of tourism.
3. **Investment and financing:** “Attracting private and public investment in rural tourism, including subsidies, grants, and soft loans for small businesses and start-ups in the tourism sector helps to improve the quality and diversity of services, as well as stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship” (Petromen et al., 2023). The long-term investment can result in job creation, economic development, and the growth of infrastructure that are advantageous to both visitors and local people, resulting to develop the well-being of rural places as a whole.

Figure 5

Several strategies to mitigate the challenges

8. Which one of these strategies are important to mitigate these problems?

19 ответов

Note: while asking some people, they suggested that the best strategy to boost rural tourism is turned out by investing and financing (78,9%). The other two suggestions are chosen like 63,2% and 31,6%.

Conclusion

Research in Uzbekistan’s rural tourism sector focuses on its considerable prospects for social and economic development. The country’s unusual cultural and natural heritage can create several doable actions to strengthen this tourism field. Nevertheless, its implementation necessitates crucial attention to the infrastructural constraints, a lack of qualified personnel, and environmental problems so as to meet the needs as well as the desires of tourists and local citizens to encourage them to come to rural areas.

In the future, by creating and following some brief strategies, such as infrastructure development, investment and financing, and training and professional development, rural tourism can be the vital component of economy in Uzbekistan, providing to get better the quality of rural tourism life, protecting cultural and natural heritage.

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